

Thursday, January 15, 2026

Follow the news here: [ECONOMY](#)[EXPERT CORNER](#)[FINANCE](#)[STOCK](#)[DIGITAL
LIFESTYLE](#)[REAL ESTATE](#)

ECONOMY

Data coordination in national transformation

14/01/2026 15:18

[Follow Financial Investments on Google News](#)

(DTTC) - Growth can come from integration, but national capacity only develops when the system is effectively coordinated. Data and strategic coordination are no longer just management tools, but the core foundation of development.

Over the past two decades, Vietnam has been successful in economic integration. Exports have increased rapidly, foreign investment has flowed abundantly, and its position in the global value chain has become increasingly prominent.

However, behind that bright picture lies a thought-provoking paradox: high growth but slow productivity growth, low domestic value added, and an economy vulnerable to new barriers in global trade.

From the “ income trap ” to the “ transformation capacity trap ”

The term "middle-income trap" is often used to describe a situation where many countries experience rapid growth in the early stages but then stagnate and fail to reach high-income status. However, the core issue in this situation lies not in income levels, but in the transformative capacity of the economy.

A country may export heavily, attract a strong influx of FDI, and achieve high growth over a long period. However, if the majority of value added is generated abroad, and if

domestic businesses fail to learn and climb higher up the value chain, then that growth is very fragile.

As the advantage of low labor costs gradually diminishes and global standards become increasingly stringent, the growth model will be stuck at the threshold of transformation.

In other words, Vietnam is facing a “transformation capacity trap”: there is integration but not enough capacity building; there are reforms but they do not accumulate into systemic strength. In this state, growth may continue, but it does not generate enough endogenous momentum for long-term upgrading.

The root cause lies in the fact that the market cannot solve the problem of upgrading capabilities on its own. Pioneering businesses bear the costs of testing and the risk of failure, while the benefits are easily copied. If the State does not play a role in organizing learning, coordinating risks, and guiding upgrades, then investment in new capabilities will always be lower than what society needs.

Integration, reform, and knowledge, if not well organized and coordinated, will not automatically translate into sustainable development capabilities. Vietnam has no shortage of efforts, but is limited in its ability to transform these resources into endogenous strengths that can be accumulated over time.

Therefore, industrial policy is not about selecting industries to prioritize, but about designing specific upgrade tasks: with clear objectives, measurable indicators, feedback mechanisms, and enforcement discipline. In essence, development is not just about expanding production, but a process of coordinating capacity at the systemic level.

National transformation capacity encompasses many important layers of capabilities, but two central ones are strategic coordination and data capacity. Strategic coordination capacity is demonstrated by the State's ability to correctly identify key upgrade challenges, integrate policies, allocate resources, set targets, and ensure effective implementation. Without coordination, reforms will be fragmented, policies will overlap, and resources will be dispersed.

At a deeper level, data capability is the cognitive capacity of the system. When data is standardized, interconnected, and used effectively, the government can clearly identify

bottlenecks, accurately measure results, and adjust policies more quickly. Conversely, if data is fragmented and unreliable, strategic coordination becomes merely a formality.

These capabilities are like the "brain and nervous system" of the development process. Without them, efforts in science and technology, production, or integration would struggle to create genuine transformation.

In reality, Vietnam's integration has been very successful thanks to the FDI sector. Foreign businesses account for a large portion of export turnover, helping the economy to expand rapidly. However, the downside is that linkages with domestic businesses are still weak, causing domestic value-added to increase slowly.

Participating in global value chains is therefore a necessary condition, but not sufficient. Without supplier upgrading programs, and without mastering standards, testing, and processes, domestic businesses will only be at the low-value stages. In that case, exports may increase rapidly, but capacity will not increase proportionally.

A similar problem arises with science and technology. Innovation does not automatically generate development if it is fragmented and detached from production and market demand. Experience from many ASEAN countries shows that when technology diffusion from FDI is weak, R&D investment is low, and industrial policies are ineffective, the economy easily falls into the middle-technology trap.

Therefore, the core question is not whether there is innovation, but whether that innovation is linked to upgrading production capacity, standards, and position in the value chain.

In the new context, access to international markets no longer depends solely on tariffs or shipping costs. It is increasingly linked to smart logistics, data traceability, and compliance with standards, making data a key competitive factor.

Without building data capabilities as a systemic capability, digital reforms and e-government initiatives will remain superficial, failing to create long-term development advantages and making it even harder for the economy to overcome the transformation trap.

From “ expanding production ” to “building capacity ”

Vietnam needs to shift from simply attracting factories and manufacturing projects to working with businesses to build and enhance long-term economic capacity.

This means that it's not just about expanding scale or increasing production, but about proactively organizing targeted upgrade programs so that endogenous capacity is formed, accumulated, and disseminated throughout the entire economy.

The core of this approach is the design of specific upgrade tasks, where competence is the central goal rather than simply pursuing short-term output targets. Each task needs to be linked to clear requirements regarding quality, standards, skills, and learning capacity, thereby creating both pressure and motivation for genuine upgrades, avoiding superficial growth.

Simultaneously, the development of a domestic supplier system must be placed within a rigorous standardization and measurement framework. Only when domestic businesses gradually master the processes, improve reliability, and meet increasingly high technical standards can the proportion of domestic value added increase sustainably.

At a higher level, science and technology need to be directly oriented towards the actual upgrading needs of production and the market, rather than fragmented innovation detached from the absorption capacity of businesses. Innovation only truly becomes a driving force for development when it contributes to solving key bottlenecks in technology, standards, and productivity.

Ultimately, the process of building and upgrading capacity can only operate effectively when data capabilities and strategic coordination are built as the foundation of development governance. This is essential for the system to accurately identify bottlenecks, measure results correctly, and adjust policies in a timely and consistent manner.

Vietnam's development path is not lacking in opportunities, but there is also little room left for growth in the old way. In a competitive world increasingly driven by capability, data, and speed, the key to development lies not in doing more, but in doing the right things and doing them thoroughly.

Only then will integration truly become a springboard for national transformation, and growth be transformed into sustainable endogenous strength of the economy.

When data capabilities and strategic coordination are placed at the heart of development governance, Vietnam can not only overcome the “transformation trap,” but

also open up a higher-quality, sustainable, and more self-reliant growth trajectory in the long term.

RELATED NEWS

- » Enhancing the ability to adapt to international changes.
- » The numbers speak volumes about the achievements of 40 years of reform.
- » Risk management is a key factor in achieving growth targets.

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien

- Endogenous
- Metabolism
- Coordination
- Domestic company
- Arrive at the destination
- FDI
- Upgrade
- Reform
- Rapid increase
- Key

COMMENT

Enter your comment

Please type in Vietnamese with diacritics.

SUBMIT A COMMENT

OTHER NEWS

Businesses operating on e-commerce platforms are also concerned about taxes.

4 hours ago

(DTTC) - The e-commerce sector continues to make a strong contribution to the state budget. Therefore, government agencies continue to improve management to create a favorable and compliant business environment.

18 GIỜ NGÀY 14-1: Loạt dự án định hình cấu trúc mới cho TPHCM

14/01/2026 18:00

(ĐTTCO) - Bản tin 18 giờ hôm nay có các nội dung nổi bật: Cấp tập triển khai các dự án đường sắt trọng điểm; Chính phủ giao chỉ tiêu nhà ở xã hội cho TPHCM.